

Statistical literacy to empower coexistence within Brazilian semiarid region

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The Brazilian semiarid region is characterized by high temperatures and evaporation, in which during periodical crises, political actions to combating drought proved to be corrupt and ineffective, placing the population in vulnerability. Coexistence within the semiarid is a political approach that supports public policies to recover respect for the cultural diversity of peoples and territories, sustainability, agroecology, and food sovereignty. This project aims to investigate possibilities for the development of statistical literacy in a collaborative context of continuous teacher education with participants who teach in the semiarid region, intending to develop pedagogical activities that contribute to re-signify understandings of the paradigm of coexistence.

Introduction

This project intends to approach this statistical literacy perspective with elementary school teachers who live and teach in the Brazilian semiarid, which is a geographic region characterized by high annual averages of temperature (27° C) and evaporation (2,000 mm), with rainfall up to 800 mm per year (Lima, Cavalcante & Perez-Marin, 2011). The Brazilian semiarid is comprised of multicultural activities and territories, as well as a unique biome called *Caatinga* (which in Tupi-Guarani language means White Forest). The Brazilian semiarid comprises 969,589.4 km² which is equivalent to 11% of national territory.

The occupation of semiarid by Europeans began in the 16th century. The colonizers introduced unsuitable cultural practices, such as agriculture based on deforestation on the banks of water sources, burning, and exotic crop plantation. These activities are still current in several areas. However, due to the economical practices being unsuitable for the semiarid climate and soil, the social situation for most populations of the semiarid becomes a serious issue during longer drought periods. During these crises, it is common to develop ineffective temporary governmental projects, but this kind of projects it is just as a political instrument of domination and alienation, as well as a promoter of corruption. This problem has historically been used for political purposes.

From the 1990s, social movements and non-governmental organizations began to develop an alternative political project which we called *coexistence within the semiarid* to reduce historical problems, such as disputes over water resources and monopolization of arable land.

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The perspective of *coexistence within the semiarid* gives value to the processes of understanding these sociocultural aspects to plan, elaborate and carry out actions in search of the good living together. Therefore, the interventions must aim to rescue respect for the cultural diversity of the various existing peoples and territories, building the sustainability of water resources and a relationship between nature and agroecological practices, coexistence technologies and food sovereignty.

Silva (2006) identifies five meanings for the *coexistence within the semiarid*:

Meanings	Descriptions
1. Coexistence with the Environment	Management and sustainable use of natural resources in the ecosystem, without making their reproduction unfeasible, considering the balance of the common space experienced.
2. Coexistence Economy	Capacity for sustainable use of natural and cultural potential in productive activities that are appropriate to the environment.
3. Coexistence with the quality of life	To be able to identify the satisfaction of fundamental needs as a condition for expanding human capacities and improving the quality of life, conceived as a reduction in inequalities, poverty, and misery.
4. Coexistence Culture	Valuing and rebuilding local population knowledge about the environment in which they live, its specificities, weaknesses, and potential.
5. Political Dimension	Mobilization of civil society, through networks of social movements and organizations, which promote the dissemination of social values of coexistence within Semi-arid and fight for the improvement of its economic and sociocultural conditions.

Table 1: The five meanings of *coexistence within semiarid*

Considering the context of Brazilian semiarid and the possible relationship with mathematics and statistics as discussed by Skovsmose (2021), we might ask the following questions: How can statistical literacy strengthen the political project of coexistence within the Brazilian semiarid from a critical and liberating perspective? What aspects were historically used to reinforce stigma and prejudice towards this region and its people? What is the role of mathematics in this process? As much in the possibilities of transformation and change as in its uses as a tool of oppression?

The general objective of this doctoral research project is to investigate how to utilize the theoretical-methodological assumptions of statistical literacy to promote the problematization of sociopolitical aspects and thereby empower the political project of coexistence with the semiarid.

The roles of mathematics and statistics to empower the coexistence with the semiarid

Skovsmose (2021) argues that the world faces more and more large-scale crises such as environmental ones, which might include those which happen in the Brazilian semiarid. The

author identifies at least three different types of relationships between mathematics and crises: mathematics *can picture a crisis*; *can constitute a crisis*; and *can format a crisis*. The political and economic interests play a decisive role to develop different crisis discourses about the reality, which can be based on mathematical and statistical arguments. For example, for over one century political actions to the semi-arid emphasised *the combating of drought*, as it could benefit a hegemonic minority of wealthier groups dominating the semi-arid. Then, in this case the statistical data is used to describe the extent of the drought, the resources people need, and somehow manipulate the reality. But also, Skovsmose considers that mathematics (and statistics) can play transformative roles in regards with crises if they support human-centred lines of arguing and actions. Statistics can support important social values, such as democracy and argument based on scientific evidence (Engel, 2019).

However, statistics can also be used to justify certain narratives by manipulating data representations that can emphasize or disguise some statistics in news (Monteiro & Ainley, 2010). In addition to that, there are disseminations of misinformation and malinformation associated with fabricated statistics, deliberately created to harm a people, social groups, organizations, or countries (Carmi, Yates, Lockley, & Pawluczuk, 2020).

Therefore, we understand that it is necessary to problematize the perceptions of how statistics can be used, either correctly and ethically, faithfully to the reality to be analysed, or in an unethical way, with the aim of pretending to validate distorted realities, favouring individual and antisocial interests, distant from the truths of the facts.

The secret language of statistics, with so much appeal to our “fact-based” culture, is used to sensationalize, inflate, confuse, and oversimplify. Statistical methods and terms are needed to report data on social and economic trends, business conditions, “opinion”, research, censuses. But without writers who use the words honestly and comprehensively, and without readers who know what they mean, the result can only be semantic absurdity. (Huff, 1993, p. 8)

In a panorama of contradictions and pitfalls, in which the biased uses of statistics can have strong implications in the social, economic, cultural, political, and historical contexts, we point out that statistical literacy is particularly important to achieve critical elements that can provide conditions to understand, transform, reflect and act up these controversial contexts.

Statistical literacy is “a stand-alone complex competency with many unique elements, well beyond knowing statistics per se. Further, I argue that statistical literacy, and its many building blocks, are seldom or insufficiently addressed in regular statistics or mathematics instruction” (Gal, 2021, p. 26). This competency is causally related to people’s attitudes towards the countless statistical information that surrounds them daily and how they critically evaluate graphs, infographics, tables, charts, statistical data from journalistic, scientific, and informational texts. Gal (2002, p. 2) argues:

the term “statistical literacy” refers broadly to two interrelated components, primarily (a) people’s ability to interpret and critically evaluate statistical information, data-related arguments, or stochastic phenomena, which they may encounter in diverse contexts, and when relevant (b) their ability to discuss or communicate their reactions to such statistical information, such as their understanding of the meaning of the information, their opinions about the implications of this information, or their concerns regarding the acceptability of given conclusions.

Following the perspective of statistical literacy (Gal, 2002), our focus is on mobilizing among the participants the structural elements: elements of knowledge (literacy, statistics, mathematics, and context) and elements of disposition (beliefs and attitudes, and criticality).

In this context of ideological, political, cultural, economic dispute between political perspectives, narratives are constituted as background for the use of statistical elements for validation, confrontation, imposition, and refutation of the facts presented by each side. It is in this aspect that we set out to investigate possibilities to enhance the paradigm of living with the semi-arid using the elements of statistical literacy.

Theoretical and methodological construction of research study

The theoretical-methodological construction process that we are proposing to carry out, seeks to articulate three interrelated perspectives, statistical literacy, *the paradigm of living with the semi-arid* and the continuing teacher education.

We intend to propose a qualitative study based on a research-action type according to Tripp (2005). This type of research produces an analysis of reality while seeking to transform it through an intervention. Therefore, this project aims to contribute to the potentiation of *the coexistence within the semi-arid*, using the elements of statistical literacy. For that reason, we decided to have an investigative structure as part of an activity of continuous teacher education which consisted of contextualized problem situations related to specificities of Brazilian semi-arid. The referred continuing education will count on the participation of teachers and professors who teach statistics in basic education level in the semi-arid territories.

The development of formative activities with teachers is based on three theoretical perspectives. Firstly, we dialogue with contextualized education for living with the semi-arid region (ECSAB), a theoretical perspective that emerged from the context of the *paradigm of coexistence*, which carry out studies, pedagogical resources, and teacher education activities within the context of the Paradigm of Coexistence (Lima, 2008).

Another perspective was that of the investigative research cycle originally proposed by Wild and Pfannkuch (1999) and adapted by Guimarães and Gitirana (2013). These authors argue that an experience with engagement in statistical research, following the cycle and going through its stages in a critical and contextualized way, is a fundamental educational activity for the construction of statistical literacy.

A third perspective with which we dialog is proposed by Watson and Callingham (2003) who presents an analytical framework composed of six levels of positioning in relation to statistical literacy. It will help us to create the action research experiences, as well as to analyse whatever data produced through the project.

The participants will be six basic education teachers who teach statistics in public schools belonging to the semi-arid territory. We called our initial approach with the participants as a *recognition step*, which consists of to know more about teachers' professional and academic backgrounds, as well as their knowledge and perspectives about semi-arid socio-political aspects. This step will be developed by carrying out individual interviews.

A second stage is to propose to the teachers to participate in a cooperative group. The meetings will be based on a focus group approach in which will produce data about teachers'

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perceptions, opinions, attitudes, critical interpretations, and beliefs. We plan to develop at least four meetings with an estimated duration of 2:30 hours.

During the focus group meetings, we will discuss the five meanings for the *coexistence within semiarid* associated with statistical literacy aspects. The meeting will be activities in which are involved in semiarid socio-political statistical contexts, which include statistical data. Table 2 presents examples of data which might be used to problematize.

Some social indicators of the Brazilian semiarid region
<i>Division of semiarid lands suitable for agriculture</i>
About 1.5 million farming families (28.82% of all Brazilian farming families) occupy only 4.2% of agricultural land in the semiarid region. While 1.3% of rural establishments with more than 1,000 hectares (called <i>latifundios</i>) hold 38% of semiarid territory.
<i>The economic situation of population</i>
The majority of Brazilians (59.1%) in extreme poverty are in the Northeast where the semiarid is located. Most of this population (52.5%) live in rural areas, and 4 out of 10 extremely poor people are between 0 and 14 years old (IBGE, 2010).
The vast majority of semiarid municipalities (60.09%) of the, with more than nine million inhabitants, the Human Development Index (HDI) varies from Very Low to Low. The HDI considers indicators of longevity, education and income. All towns in the Semi-arid region had a lower Municipal human development index (HDI-M) than in Brazilian national rate, which is 0.727.

Table 2: Social indicators of the Brazilian semiarid region

The information presented on Table 1 can be a starting point to interpret the semiarid reality based on statistical data. To begin the reflections, the researcher would ask questions, such as:

What do you think about this information?

Do you think it is reliable information?

Do you think that this information can stereotype people who live in the semiarid region?

What have you heard, during your life, about the semiarid region?

Do you believe in these opinions?

Have you ever used statistical data to describe the semiarid?

What kind of information have you used to describe the people who live in semiarid?

What did you want to argue?

What other data can we use to demonstrate the potential of this region?

Do you think the way this data is used by politicians leads to more inequality?

How can aspects of statistical literacy help in building a dignified understanding of this region and these people?

The researcher will mediate the group proposing reflections, reviewing understandings and possible stereotypes, perceptions living, existing and resisting in the Brazilian semiarid.

Provisional considerations

The articulation between the theoretical perspectives of contextualized education for coexistence within the Brazilian semiarid and statistical literacy, suggests a promising path for the potentializing coexistence paradigm. In this sense, we expect that it is possible to transform and reframe the understandings and practices of teachers and professors of Brazilian semiarid so that they become mobilizing agents of this perspective.

We believe in the proposal under construction and in its effectiveness, so that we can disarm, disturb the hegemonic discourses, and introduce provocations into the debate, problematizing and denaturing exclusionary and silencing practices, so that we can dismantle the accepted and naturalized imagery about Brazilian semiarid.

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